

Amino Derivatives of Tellurium Tetrachloride. Part II. Salts of Chlorotellurous Acid with Piperidine, Piperizine, and 2-Aminopyridine

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The amino derivatives of tellurium tetrachloride with some secondary and tertiary amines, heterocyclic bases, and salts of chlorotellurous acid with piperidine, piperizine, and 2-aminopyridine have been prepared; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

The preparation and properties of the compounds of tellurium tetrachloride with aromatic primary amines have been studied in Part I'. The work has been extended to study the action of TeCl_4 on some secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases under similar conditions. Besides, the formation of piperidinium, piperizinium, and 2-aminopyridinium chlorotellurites has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tellurium tetrachloride was prepared from its elements and purified by distillation. The other chemicals used were of E. Merck's or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality.

General Method of Preparation of Amino Compounds.—Solutions of tellurium tetrachloride and the amine were prepared in benzene and the amine solution was gradually added to TeCl_4 solution with constant shaking. With all the amines the precipitate formed settled down immediately except in cases of methylaniline, piperizine, and 2-aminopyridine, where ethereal solutions of the amines were added to TeCl_4 solutions in benzene in order to get semicrystalline precipitates. The product formed was filtered, washed thoroughly with benzene till free of the reactants, dried at the room temperature in a vacuum desiccator, analysed, and its properties were studied.

Tellurium was estimated as TeO_2 by precipitating it in very dilute acetic acid medium, chlorine by Piria and Schiff's method after removing tellurium, and nitrogen by Dumas' method.

General Properties.—The compounds formed with tellurium tetrachloride and secondary and tertiary amines are in many respects similar to those formed with the primary amines'. These are generally yellowish, amorphous compounds which decompose on heating and are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in acids. The compounds obtained with *p*-aminodiethylaniline and diphenylamine are sparingly soluble in methanol. These compounds are fairly stable in dry air but decompose to tellurous acid when come in contact with water. The compound formed with *p*-aminodiethylaniline is hygroscopic.

All these compounds seem to add up ammonia molecules when suspended in benzene and dry ammonia is passed through them.

TABLE I

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.*	% Tellurium.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
Methyl-A†	$(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH})_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Greenish yellow	114°	26.30	26.38	29.28	29.34	5.87	5.79
Ethyl-A	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH})_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Grey	118°	24.61	24.94	27.55	27.75	5.38	5.47
Benzyl-A	$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Light yellow	137°	20.64	20.75	22.26	22.34	4.33	4.40
Diethyl-A	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2)_2\text{TeCl}_4$	"	141°	30.25	30.46	33.69	33.92	6.52	6.69
p-Aminodimethyl-A	$[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2]_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Red	126°	31.31	31.46	34.86	35.00	6.86	6.90
p-Aminodimethyl-A	$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2]_2\text{TeCl}_4$	"	..	29.28	29.40	32.52	32.75	6.27	6.45
Diphenylamine	$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}]_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Light yellow	129°	20.82	21.00	23.30	23.36	4.58	4.60
Quinoline	$(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N})_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Cream	115°	23.96	24.18	26.78	26.91	5.18	5.31
Piperidine	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N})_2\text{TeCl}_4$	"	163°	28.91	29.02	32.12	32.30	6.29	6.37
α-Picoline	$(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Yellow	118°	27.82	28.00	31.08	31.16	6.07	6.14
Nicotine	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Red	..	29.40	29.56	32.78	32.90	6.53	6.49
Piperazine	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_2\text{TeCl}_4$	Lemon-yellow	156°	35.81	35.88	39.86	39.90	7.92	7.87
2-Aminopyridine	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2\text{TeCl}_4$	" "	188°	35.01	35.00	39.00	39.05	7.66	7.70

†A denotes aniline.

*Melt with decomposition.

When heated alone, they afford a greyish white sublimate which is acidic, soluble in water, and responds to the test for chlorine and the corresponding bases. On heating with soda-lime, the corresponding amine deposits on the cooler part of the test tube.

An examination of the results shows that tellurium forms complexes with the co-ordination number of 6; the structure of these compounds appears to be similar to those formed with primary amines, as shown in Part I¹.

Piperidinium, Piperizinium, and 2-Aminopyridinium Tetrachlorotellurites.—These salts were prepared by the method described by Anasley *et al.*². A known amount of TeCl_4 , strong HCl, and the base were mixed in a conical flask and the solution was concentrated on a water bath at 70-80° when a crystalline product was obtained. It was recrystallised from strong HCl, filtered, and analysed. The analysis shows the formation of following compounds:

Piperidinium hexachlorotellurite as shining yellow microcrystals, m.p. 141° (decomp.). [Found: Te, 24.52; N, 5.34; Cl, 41.58. $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{NH})_2\text{TeCl}_6$ requires Te, 24.89; N, 5.46; Cl, 41.55%].

Piperizinium pentachlorotellurite as shining greenish yellow crystals (decomp. at 213°). [Found: Te, 32.22; N, 6.95; Cl, 45.21. $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{H})\text{TeCl}_5$ requires Te, 32.54; N, 7.14; Cl, 45.27%].

2-Aminopyridinium pentachlorotellurite as yellow needles (decomp. at 173°). [Found: Te, 31.63; N, 6.86; Cl, 44.47. $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{H})\text{TeCl}_5$ requires Te, 31.89; N, 6.99; Cl, 44.36%].

These compounds were also prepared by dissolving the corresponding tetrachlorotellurium (IV) complexes in minimum quantity of warm HCl (conc.) and cooling.

The compounds are stable, crystalline, insoluble in common organic solvents but readily soluble in dilute acids. These are rapidly hydrolysed by water, forming a precipitate of tellurous acid.

Tellurium is well known to form two types of complex salts, $\text{M}[\text{TeCl}_5]$ and $\text{M}_2[\text{TeCl}_6]$, which are always derived from tetrachloride. The piperizinium pentachlorotellurite (I), 2-aminopyridinium pentachlorotellurite (II), and piperidinium hexachlorotellurite (III) may be represented as:

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2. Anasley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2802; 1955, 2803; 1951, 832.